

crystallised from alcohol. m.p. 188-89° (Found : C, 68.75; H, 5.63. $C_{28}H_{26}O_8$ requires C, 68.57; H, 5.31%).

2, 4-Bis[ω , β' (ethyl- α' -carbethoxy β' -p-methoxyphenyl propionate) acetyl] resorcinol : Prepared as before from 2, 4-di(p-methoxy cinnamoyl) resorcinol (1 g) and diethyl malonate (10 ml) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.5 g in 5 ml alcohol and crystallised from alcohol gave m. p. 115° (Found : C, 63.76; H, 5.94. $C_{40}H_{46}O_{14}$ requires C, 63.98; H, 6.13%).

2,4-Bis[ω , β' -(p-methoxyphenyl propionic acid) acetyl] resorcinol : Prepared from the above compound as before and crystallised from alcohol gave m.p. 175° (Found : C, 64.29; H, 5.72. $C_{30}H_{30}O_{10}$ requires C, 64.45; H, 5.45%).

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LTA Cyclization of Some 2-benzothiazolyl Hydrazones

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SOME of the benzothiazole derivatives are well known fungicidal and bactericidal compounds.

Similarly s-triazoles are also known as physiologically active compounds¹. With the interest of preparing some compounds with a condensed system, Triazolobenzothiazoles, the work was undertaken. The most convenient well known procedure for preparing parent system was aza heterocyclic hydrazino compound treated with acidic cyclodehydrating agents for ring closure². For other compounds oxidative cyclization of hydrazones can be carried out.

In earlier studies, Leadtetraacetate was looked upon solely as a mean of cyclizing hydrazones. S-triazoloisoquinoline³, s-triazolobenzoxazoles⁴, s-triazolopyridine⁵ and s-triazolopyrazine⁶ were prepared by this method. Butler and Scott^{7,8} pointed out the existence of competitive acetoxylation process during LTA treatment. These authors reported that the products which Bower and Doyle⁹ considered as s-triazolobenzothiazole contained a molecule of acetic acid of solvation. Barton and Coworkers¹⁰ confirmed the same. Some of the hydrazones prepared in our laboratory were subjected to LTA oxidation. The reaction was carried out in acetic acid solvent. The crude product thus isolated refluxed with benzene. The benzene soluble and insoluble parts were separated. Benzene insoluble part could not be analysed since it was somewhat muddy and sticky in nature. Perhaps this may contain acetoxyated part. The soluble part was a cyclized compound. The same was confirmed by using Br_2 /acetic acid as cyclizing agent with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles. Compared to triazolobenzoxazoles cyclization is taking place without much difficulty may be perhaps due to more polarizable and less electronegative sulphur in the heterocyclic system. Our results are in agreement with Butler, Scott and Barton et al. The melting point and analytical data are in agreement with cyclized structures¹¹. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—3-SUBSTITUTED-S-TRIAZOLO(3,4-b)-BENZOTHIAZOLES

Sl. No.	Substituent	Molecular Formula	M.P. °C	Solvent for crys.	Yield %	% N found
1.	Phenyl	$C_{14}H_9N_3S$	185	benzene	48	16.84
2.	2'-hydroxyphenyl	$C_{14}H_9N_3OS$	160	alcohol	56	15.80
3.	4'-hydroxyphenyl	$C_{14}H_9N_3OS$	165	alcohol	42	15.78
4.	2-Pyridyl	$C_{12}H_6N_4S$	232	benzene	50	22.24
5.	2-Thienyl	$C_{12}H_6N_3S_2$	145	benzene	52	16.14

Experimental

Benzothiazolyl hydrazones prepared by taking equimolar proportions of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole and required aldehyde in ethanol. The details were published¹².

Cyclization of 2-benzothiazolyl hydrazones to

(i) 3-Phenyl-s-triazolo(3,4-b)benzothiazole :

The 2-phenyl benzothiazolyl hydrazone (1.0 g) was taken in (8 ml) of glacial acetic acid. Lead-tetraacetate (2.5 g) was added in portions to the above solution. The mixture was boiled for 20 minutes and then poured over cold water, it filtered. The residue was faint greenish colour. The crude ppt was taken in benzene refluxed for half an hour. The insoluble part was separated by filtration.

NOTES

(ii) 3-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl)-*s*-triazolo(3,4-*b*)benzothiazole :

The 2-*p*-hydroxyphenyl benzothiazolyl hydrazone prepared (by condensing *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole) (1.20 g) was taken in (8 ml) acetic acid. Leadtetraacetate (3.2 g) was added to the acetic acid solution and refluxed for half an hour. The contents were poured over water. The compound separated as per the procedure described in (i).

(iii) 3-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl)-*s*-triazolo(3, 4-*b*)benzothiazole :

(1 gm) *o*-Hydroxyphenyl benzothiazolyl hydrazone was taken in (8 ml) acetic acid and (3.2 g) Leadtetraacetate refluxed for 15 minutes. Isolation as described in (i) compound recrystallised from alcohol.

(iv) 3(2'-Pyridyl)-*s*-triazolo(3, 4-*b*)benzothiazole :

(1 gm) hydrazone (3.2 g) Leadtetraacetate and (12 ml) acetic acid refluxed for 20 minutes. Isolation as in (i). Recrystallised from benzene.

(v) 3(2'-Thienyl)-*s*-triazolo(3,4-*b*)benzothiazole :

(1 gm) Thienyl benzothiazolyl hydrazone (3.5 g) Leadtetraacetate and (10 ml) acetic acid refluxed for 30 minutes. The compound recrystallised from benzene.

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Studies Related to 1-Substituted Anilino-Malonyl-3-Methyl-4-(*o*-Nitrophenyl-Azo)-2-Pyrazolin-5-ones*

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PYRAZOLONE derivatives have often shown therapeutic^{1,2,3,4} activities and have been used as dyes⁵. Rathore and Ittyerah⁶ have synthesised acid hydrazides of malon-anilic acid series with the view to assess their antitubercular activity. Though vast amount of work has been done on the synthesis of pyrazolone-azo dyes, no studies have appeared on the formation of dyes using acid hydrazides of malon-anilic acid series.

Our interest was, therefore, focussed on the synthesis of new pyrazolone-azo dyes having structural features of acid hydrazides of malon-anilic acid series and pyrazolone-azo group.

Treatment of *o*-nitrobenzenediazoniumchloride with ethylacetoacetate gave ethyl- α -(*o*-nitrophenyl-azo)acetoacetate which on condensation with malon-anilic acid hydrazides furnished new dyes of the type I. Considerable improvement in the size of the yield of the dyes(I) has been observed when condensations were done in presence of a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid.

Data concerning the dyes are presented in Table 1. These dyes are high melting yellow or orange in colour and are soluble in common organic solvents.

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